

Revenue Stickers, Taxation and Improvements

Arjun Dahal

Mental Asylum of Education

P.O. Box 1

Gauradaha, Jhapa

Abstract: Revenue stickers are important stickers in trade, which are levied on goods, to provide the information about goods, and taxation. In this paper, we have attempted to improve the revenue stickers.

Introduction:

Let us begin our discussion with a sample of Revenue sticker(excise stickers and other types)as shown in figure below (Fig:a)

Fig:a

In our sample sticker of Revenue, patent number of invention is mentioned to provide information to customers about any products, regarding how they were invented, and with a aim of industrializing the patented applications.

Similarly in sample "Rs__" is mentioned to provide description about taxable amount, which customers do pay while buying any goods. "Types of Goods" is mentioned to provide information about type of goods, like as liquors and tobacco products, for which excise stickers are used more.

Similarly Bar Codes, and QR codes are for consumers to find out description about manufacturing companies, outlets where goods can be found, as well as about ingredients in goods. Ingredients in goods, can be found in most of goods, and by means of Bar Codes and QR codes, we have attempted to digitalize the information in any products.

In case of Nepal:

In Nepal too, excise stickers can be found, and by means of sample excise (revenue) stickers, we have attempted to discuss, about digitalization of products.

Regarding Taxation:

In Nepal, Permanent Account Number (PAN) is used as taxpayer identification number, where unique number is assigned to each individual as taxpayers. Thus by means of PAN number we can find how much tax did we payed (based on P-PAN (personal PAN)) of any individual, even if they don't have business PAN. Similarly P-PAN, and B-PAN (Business PAN) both would have their own importance, based on individuality without any business, and individuality(firm/organization/company) with particular business.

We shall propose Patrukaar's theory of taxation, where taxation is unified, and peoples can know, how much taxes did they payed. For this, we shall propose an app, that can scan the sample excise stickers, and provide us record about the goods that we do buy. Then that app would keep our records regarding taxation, based on our PAN number or any tax payers identification numbers, which would again be helpful in auditing, as well as finding out general economic livelihood of people, economy and taxation of nation, and health habits too. We would be able to study about health habits, based on food materials that we do eat, basically junk food items, and packed items.

Since, Nepal has three tiers of administrative system these days; Federal, Provincial, and Local, PAN number plays an important role for unifying taxation, so that peoples wouldn't need to pay taxes twice or more, depending upon tiers of administrations; either be local, provincial or Federal Level. Local levels too are found to be providing unique tax payer identification number to peoples, and either by local tax payer identification system, or by PAN number, when taxation is unified, peoples would be able to pay taxes, just once, for the taxes levied by government. De-centralization would be another factor effecting taxation, unless taxation is unified.

Same like as of Postal tickets [1], revenue stickers too can be subjected to monetary topics and transactions[2], but only for unused stickers, or unendorsed stickers. Need of app seems unnecessary, but in the present world dominated by digital means, an app would be more convenient to keep records about taxation, as well as ingredients about foods, which would not only develop healthy habit,

promote consumer's rights, but would even allow us to know about nutrition by means of app, instead of writing down on plain paper.

References:

1. Arjun Dahal. (2021). Development of Postal Office Theory. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5256117>
2. Arjun Dahal. (2021). Digital Currencies and Transactions at Glance. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5255840>
3. Arjun Dahal. (2021). Manufacture of Products, and Consumer's Right. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4922616>

Comments and Acknowledgements:

I had submitted hand-written application to Inland Revenue Department of Nepal, but didn't get their response, regarding revenue stickers and their improvements and Patrukaar's Theory of taxation.